

THE USE OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *Modern technologies of teaching foreign languages accumulate successful information of each of them, enable the teacher to adjust any technology in accordance with the structure, functions, content, goals and objectives of training in the particular group of students. Modern educational technologies play a vital role in teaching a foreign languages. This article will describe using contemporary educational technology in teaching foreign languages.*

Keywords: *contemporary educational technologies, foreign languages, communication and innovative technology.*

The most vital tool for communication, language is essential to human civilization's existence and growth. The modern shifts in social interactions and communication methods (the usage of new digital technologies) necessitate that students' communicative ability and philological preparation be improved. They needed to be able to share their ideas with other communicators in a variety of contexts while adhering to speech norms and the language system, and they needed to select communicative behaviors that were appropriate for the real-world communication scenarios. Stated differently, the primary goal of learning a foreign language is to develop communicative competence, or the capacity to engage in interpersonal and cross-cultural conversation with native speakers. An essential component of education is the educational aspect.

The most effective way to create an educational environment that allows for person-oriented interaction amongst all participants in the educational process is to employ modern educational technology to help students develop their communicative skills in language acquisition. It is evident that utilizing a single educational technology, no matter how ideal, will not produce the best circumstances for pupils' talents to be revealed and developed or for teachers' creativity to flourish.

The use of educational technologies in teaching a foreign language offers numerous benefits for both educators and learners. Here are some of the key reasons why integrating educational technologies is important:

Enhanced Engagement: Educational technologies provide interactive and multimedia-rich learning experiences that capture learners' attention and foster active engagement. Interactive activities, games, and simulations make language learning more enjoyable and motivating, leading to increased participation and retention of language skills.

Access to Authentic Resources: Digital technologies grant learners access to authentic language resources such as videos, audio recordings, articles, and social media content from around the world. This exposure to real-life language use and cultural contexts enhances learners' language proficiency and cultural competence.

Personalized Learning Experiences: Educational technologies enable personalized learning pathways tailored to individual learners' needs, preferences, and learning styles. Adaptive learning platforms, intelligent tutoring systems, and personalized feedback mechanisms optimize learning outcomes by providing targeted support and scaffolding for each learner.

Flexibility and Convenience: Online platforms, mobile applications, and virtual classrooms offer flexibility and convenience in language learning, allowing learners to study anytime, anywhere. Learners can access course materials, participate in virtual discussions, and engage in language practice activities at their own pace and schedule.

Collaborative Learning Opportunities: Educational technologies facilitate collaboration and communication among learners, educators, and peers, regardless of geographical barriers. Online forums, social media communities, and collaborative projects enable learners to interact, share ideas, and collaborate on language learning tasks, fostering a sense of community and mutual support.

Immediate Feedback and Assessment: Digital technologies enable real-time feedback and assessment of learners' language skills, allowing educators to monitor progress, identify areas for improvement, and provide timely intervention and support. Automated grading systems, speech recognition software, and online quizzes streamline assessment processes and provide learners with immediate feedback on their performance.

Cultivation of Digital Literacy Skills: Integrating educational technologies in language teaching helps learners develop essential digital literacy skills, including information literacy, media literacy, and digital communication skills. These skills are increasingly important in today's digital age and prepare learners for success in academic, professional, and social contexts.

Preparation for Global Citizenship: Exposure to diverse language resources, cultural perspectives, and global issues through educational technologies prepares learners to become informed and engaged global citizens. Language proficiency and intercultural competence are essential skills for navigating multicultural societies, fostering cross-cultural understanding, and promoting peace and cooperation on a global scale.

Integrating modern educational technologies into the teaching process can offer numerous benefits for both educators and students. These technologies can enhance engagement by providing interactive and multimedia-rich learning experiences that cater to diverse learning styles. By incorporating tools such as interactive activities, simulations, and multimedia resources, teachers can make lessons more interesting and enjoyable for students.

Moreover, research suggests that the strategic use of educational technologies can lead to improved learning outcomes. Technologies like adaptive learning platforms and personalized feedback mechanisms enable teachers to provide tailored learning experiences that meet individual student needs. This personalization fosters a deeper understanding of the material and helps students progress at their own pace.

Educational technologies expand access to educational resources and information, particularly in contexts where traditional resources may be limited. Online libraries, digital textbooks, and open educational resources provide students with a wealth of learning materials, enriching their educational experience.

In today's digital age, digital literacy and technological proficiency are essential skills for success. By integrating educational technologies into their teaching practices, educators can help prepare students for the demands of the 21st-century workforce and society.

However, it's crucial for teachers to approach the integration of educational technologies thoughtfully, considering factors such as accessibility, equity, privacy, and pedagogical effectiveness. Ultimately, the decision to use educational technologies should be guided by a commitment to enhancing student learning and fostering meaningful educational experiences.

The use of modern educational technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language has become increasingly popular and effective in recent years. These technologies can enhance the learning experience for students by providing interactive and engaging activities, personalized learning paths, and real-time feedback.

Some examples of contemporary educational technologies that can be used in teaching a foreign language include:

1. Language learning apps: Apps like Duolingo, Babbel, and Rosetta Stone offer interactive lessons, quizzes, and games to help students practice vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation.

2. Online language learning platforms: Platforms like FluentU, Lingodeer, and Memrise provide a variety of multimedia resources, such as videos, podcasts, and flashcards, to help students improve their language skills.

3. Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR): VR and AR technology can create immersive language learning experiences that simulate real-world scenarios and environments, helping students practice their language skills in a more engaging way.

4. Language learning software: Programs like Anki, Quizlet, and Pimsleur offer spaced repetition algorithms and audio-based lessons to help students memorize vocabulary and improve their listening skills.

5. Online tutoring platforms: Websites like iTalki, Preply, and Verbling connect students with native speakers for one-on-one language practice sessions via video chat.

In summary, the use of modern educational technologies in teaching a foreign language can help students learn more efficiently, retain information better, and stay motivated throughout their language learning journey. It can also enrich the learning experience, engage students, and facilitate language acquisition by providing diverse, authentic, and interactive language learning opportunities. By leveraging multimedia resources effectively, teachers can create dynamic and inclusive learning environments that empower students to develop their English language skills and cultural competence.

REFERENCES

1. 1.Abrams, Z. I. (2002). Surfing to cross-cultural awareness: using Internet-mediated projects to explore cultural stereotypes. *Foreign Language Annals*, 35(2), 141–160.
2. 2.Blasszauer, J. (2001). Collaborative projects via the Internet. *Teaching English with Technology: A Journal for Teachers of English*, 1(6), 1–7.
3. 3.Fieldhouse, M. & Nicholas, D. (2008) Digital Literacy as Information Savvy: The Road to Information Literacy. In Lankshear, C. & Knobel, M. (Eds): 47-72
4. 4.РАДЖАБОВА, Д. А. MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE / Д. А. РАДЖАБОВА. — ТЕКСТ :НЕПОСРЕДСТВЕННЫЙ // МОЛОДОЙУЧЕНЫЙ. — 2017. — № 13 (147). — С. 592-595. — URL: [HTTPS://MOLUCH.RU/ARCHIVE/147/41269/](https://moluch.ru/archive/147/41269/) (ДАТАОБРАЩЕНИЯ: 23.02.2024)
5. 5.<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/modern-educational-technologies-in-teaching-foreign-languages-1>
6. 6.https://www.researchgate.net/publication/366694963_Modern_Technologies_of_Teaching_Foreign_Languages_in_the_Context_of_Digitalization_of_Foreign_Language_Education